

Pest management and control INSECTS

Insectary evaluation of insecticides to control rice stink bugs

E. A. Heinrichs, S. L. Valencia, and R. P. Basilio, International Rice Research Institute

Rice bugs (*Leptocorisa oratorius*) were reared by the method described by Valencia and Heinrichs (this issue). Rice variety IR36 plants at the flowering stage were used as test plants. Three tests were conducted.

In test 1, four panicles were sprayed. In tests 2 and 3, four hills were sprayed on a turntable. In tests 1 and 2, concentrations were based on manufacturers' recommendations. In test 3, new insecticides were compared with monocrotophos and were applied at the rate of 0.75

Table 1. Activity^a of insecticides applied as foliar sprays to control rice bugs. IIRI greenhouse, 1979.

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	Mortality (%)
<i>Test 1</i>		
<i>Effective</i>		
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	0.05	100 a
Endosulfan 35 EC	0.06	100 a
Chlorpyrifos 40 EC	0.016	100a
Phosphamidon 50 EC	0.07	100 a
Acephate 40 EC	0.09	99 a
Triazophos 40 EC	0.07	98 a
Carbaryl 85 WP	0.12	91 b
<i>Intermediate</i>		
MIPC 50 WP	0.07	74 bc
Carbophenothion 40 EC	0.09	73 bc
Methyl parathion 50 EC	0.07	56 c
Chlorpyrifos + BPMC 31.6 EC	0.14	50 c
<i>Ineffective</i>		
Carbofuran 12 F	0.01	19 d
Azinphos ethy 140 EC	0.07	3 e
MTMC 30 EC	0.11	3e
Control		3e
<i>Test 2</i>		
<i>Effective</i>		
Monocrotophos + mevinphos 20.2 EC	0.06	100 a
Diazinon 20 EC	0.21	100a

Cont'd. on next column.

Table 1 cont'd.

Insecticide	Concentration (%)	Mortality ^a (%)
Fenitrothion 30 EC	0.05	98 ab
Pirimiphos methyl 25 EC	0.03	85 b
<i>Ineffective</i>		
FMC 35001 20 EC	0.02	28 c
BPMC 50 EC	0.05	23 c
Ethion 40 EC	0.04	8 cd
Permethrin 10 EC	0.01	0 d
Control		0 d

^a Insects were placed on treated panicles 1 day after treatment and mortality recorded 48 hours after infestation. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. Effective =>80% mortality, intermediate = 50-79% mortality, ineffective = <50% mortality.

Table 2. Knockdown and residual effect of insecticides against rice bugs. IIRI greenhouse, 1979.

Insecticide	Mortality (%)		
	1 DAT	7 DAT	14 DAT
UC54229 100 Tech.	100.0 a	100.0 a	56.7 b
M 9918 20 OE	100.0 a	96.7 ab	76.7 a
M 10604 20 OE	100.0 a	86.7 b	43.3 bc
Monocrotophos 16.8 EC	100.0 a	36.1 c	20.0 c
Methiocarb 50 WP	100.0 a	20.0 cd	3.3 d
Methidathion 40 EC	93.3 a	10.0 de	0.0 d
UC 27867 50 WP	83.3 a	0.0 e	3.3 d
Cypermethrin 5 EC	56.7 b	3.3 e	0.0 d
Dioxacarb 50 WP	10.0 c	0.0 e	0.0 d
Dioxathion 96 EC	3.3 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
UC SF-1 40 F	3.3 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
RP 32861 20 EC	0.0 c	13.3 de	0.0 d
EXP 5494 25 EC	0.0 c	3.3 e	0.0 d
RH 0308 48 EC	0.0 c	0.0 e	3.3 d
RH 0994 48 EC	0.0 c	3.3 e	3.3 d
Control	0.0 c	3.3 e	0.0 d

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DAT= days after treatment.

Mass rearing of rice stink bugs

S. Valencia and E. A. Heinrichs, International Rice Research Institute

Rice bugs, *Leptocorisa* spp., occur throughout Asia. Heavy feeding on rice grains in the milky stage prevents grain development and results in unfilled

kg a.i./ha, based on 160,000 hills and 1,000 liters of spray solution per hectare.

One day after spraying, panicles were placed in a mylar film cage with 10 two-day-old female rice bug adults. Mortality was recorded 48 hours later. In test 3, residual activity was measured by determining mortality 7 and 14 days after treatment (DAT). Treatments were replicated four times.

Seven insecticides in test 1 and four in test 2 were effective ($\geq 80\%$ mortality) at the concentrations tested (Table 1). In test 3 (Table 2), UC 54229, M 9918, M 10604, methiocarb, methidathion, and UC 27867 were effective 1 DAT. M 9918 had the longest residual activity, causing 77% mortality 14 DAT. ■

grains. The primary control is spraying or dusting with insecticides. Little evaluation of insecticides for control has been published, primarily because of the difficulty of conducting field tests. We have developed a mass rearing technique for *L. oratorius* which supplies sufficient insects to evaluate insecticides in the insectary and laboratory. The method

also can be used to supply rice bugs for varietal screening and other studies.

Steps for mass rearing of *L. oratorius* follow:

- Collect adults from the field with a sweep net, verify species and sex.
- Release a group of 10 males and 12 females into an oviposition cage 97 cm tall and 27 cm in diameter (see figure). IRRI's cage consists of mylar film reinforced with two heavy gauge wire rings. The cage rests in a trough containing water to maintain high humidity. Any susceptible rice variety can serve as a food source and substrate on which insects can lay eggs. We use early-maturing variety IR36 to shorten the time required to grow plants to the ripening stage.
- Provide fresh plants in the milk grain stage once a week.
- Collect eggs from the oviposition cage daily by clipping the leaf portion containing the eggs.
- Place leaf pieces in a petri dish containing moist filter paper and store for 5 days at room temperature.
- Five days after oviposition, transfer leaf pieces with eggs to the nymph rearing cage, which is identical to the oviposition cage.
- Clip leaf pieces with eggs to the base of panicles at the milk grain stage of the rice plant in this cage. After hatching, nymphs will move up to the developing grains to feed. Change plants in this cage once a week.

A method for mass rearing *Leptocoris oratorius* for use in insecticide screening studies. IRRI, 1982.

Depending on the temperature at Los Baños, nymphs become adults in 17-33 days. Transfer some adults to the oviposition cage to maintain the colony.

The excess of 1- and 2-day-old adults

can be used for bioassay of insecticides. The 12 females in one oviposition cage will provide sufficient eggs for 2 nymph-to-adult rearing cages, producing about 300 adults/day. ■

Chemical control of the whitebacked planthopper in Pakistan

Muhammad Akram Zafar, senior subject matter specialist (Plant Protection), adaptive research farm, Sheikhpura, Pakistan

Damage from the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) *Sogatella furcifera* (Horvath) is increasing in Pakistan, particularly to high-tillering rice varieties. The only control that has been applied is minor dusting with BHC or BHC + DDT in seriously infested areas. An experiment was conducted during the 1980 wet season to identify insecticides

Insecticide control of whitebacked planthopper in Pakistan.

Treatment	Formulation	Dosage (kg a.i./ha)	Pest density (no./5 sweeps) at		Pest control (%) after	
			3 days	15 days	3 days	15 days
MIPC	50 WP spray	1.250	2	22	97	70
Carbaryl	85 SP spray	2.125	2	35	98	52
Pyridaphenthion	2% dust	0.750	5	28	93	62
BHC + DDT	10% dust	0.375 + 0.875	11	26	85	64
Control	-	-	69	74	-	-

effective for WBPH control. The trial on IR6 rice in farmers' fields in Sheikhpura was laid out in completely randomized blocks with three replications and was repeated in two dif-

ferent but climatically and topographically similar fields. Fields were heavily infested with WBPH. MIPC and carbaryl were sprayed at 375 liters/ha, and pyridaphenthion (Ofunack) and BHC +